

Chemistry of Naturally Occurring Succinic Acid Derivatives and Related Compounds*

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The 2nd of August is an important day for Chemists in India, because it is the birth day of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray. It is good for us to remember him and his work. The earlier lectures of this series were given by men who were direct students of the Acharya. Now it has become the turn of his student's students whom he used to call grand students. I am one who belongs to this category and I consider it a great privilege to give these lectures.

Acharya P. C. Ray was a pioneer in an age of pioneers. He studied chemistry in Edinburgh and made its study and research popular in India. He left students who have worked in all branches of chemistry. He was a great teacher not only in Chemistry but also in a wider sense a teacher of men. Hence the title Acharya fits him in a comprehensive sense. He took keen interest in social welfare and put into practice the twin ideals of a chemist to produce wealth and promote health. Since he was largely an iatro-chemist in out-look, I have chosen to speak, as appropriate to this occasion, on a topic related to plant drugs in which I and my collaborators have been recently interested.

INTEREST IN LICHENS AS DRUGS

Since the discovery in 1940 by Chain, Florey and others¹ that penicillin (I) was a potential chemotherapeutic agent for infectious diseases, studies on metabolic products of micro-organisms have developed rapidly. These biological products have since been named antibiotics and this term is not limited to newly found substances. Some known fungal compounds with established chemical structures were taken up again for the study of antibiotic activity. For instance, fumigatin² (II) produced by *Aspergillus fumigatus* was found to inhibit the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus anthracis*, and *Vibrio cholerae*. Further, antibiotic activity was exhibited by penicillic acid³ (III), citrinin^{4,5} (IV), mycophenolic acid^{6,7} (V), and kojic acid⁸⁻¹⁰ (VI).

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1. E. Chain, H. W. Florey, A. D. Gardner, N. G. Heatley, M. A. Jennings, J. Orr-Ewing, and A. G. Sanders, *Lancet*, 1940, 239, 228.
2. W. K. Anslow and H. Raistrick, *Biochem. J.*, 1938, 32, 687.
3. A. E. Oxford, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1942, 61, 49.
4. H. Raistrick and G. Smith, *ibid.*, 1941, 60, 828.
5. A. C. Hetherington and H. Raistrick, *Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, B 220, 269.
6. C. L. Alsberg and O. F. Black, U. S. Dept. Agr. Bureau of Plant Ind. Bull., 1913, 270.
7. H. W. Florey, K. Gilliver, M. A. Jennings, and A. G. Sanders, *Lancet*, 1946, i, 46.
8. K. Saito, *Bot. Mag. Tokyo*, 1907, 21, 249.
9. T. Yahata, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 575.
10. H. E. Morton *et al.*, *J. Bact.*, 1945, 50, 579.

Many lichens were used in medieval times for the treatment of diseases* based on the "doctrine of signatures". For example, *Peltigera canina* was used against mad dog bite, because the lichen had the appearance of a dog. *Peltigera aphthosa*, another species, the thallus of which is dotted with small wart-like structures, was recommended for children suffering from 'thrush'. *Xanthoria parietina*, being a yellow lichen, was supposed to cure jaundice. *Lobaria pulmonaria* was considered a suitable remedy for lung troubles. But an example of more valid use may be that of *Usnea* in tuberculosis, since usnic acid present in it is now found to be antibiotic.

The antimicrobial activity of orsellinic acid derivatives, like sparassol (XIV), was noted early in their study¹². It has been observed that the activity of the homologues increases with the increase in the number of carbon atoms of the alkyl substituents as can be seen in the order: orcinol (XV), divarinol (XVI), and olivetol (XVII) carboxylic acids. On the other hand, further introduction of -OH and -COOH groups decreases the activity.

12. G. A. Llano, "Economic Botany", Vol. 2, No. 1, p. 15, 1948.

13. F. Fuzikawa *et al.*, *J. Hyg. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 9, 292; *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1939, 59, 240, 242, 244, 615, 617; 1940, 60, 473; 1941, 61, 89, 191, 325, 469; 1942, 62, 61, 304, 459, 505, 508; 1943, 63, 102, 156, 255, 277; 1944, 64, 15; 1944, 64A, 19, 20, 54; 1945, 65A, 4.

(XV) : R = Me.

(XVI) : R = C₃H₇.(XVII) : R = C₃H₁₁.

(XIV)

The antibacterial activities of lichen fatty acids were studied by Asano, Kameda and others¹⁴ who reported remarkable activity in lichesterinic acid (XVIII) and related compounds. Similar activity was shown by usnic acid (XIX), atranorin (X), and fumarprotocetraric acid (XXI). Stoll and his co-workers¹⁵ found that usnic acid was active especially against *Myco. tuberculosis*. Later, Barry and Twomay¹⁶ studied the mixture of Na-salts of roccellic acid's half-esters (XXII) for their activity against *Myco. tuberculosis* and found that they inhibited their growth in broth for six weeks at a dilution of $2 \times 10^5 - 4 \times 10^5$.

(XVIII)

(XIX)

(XX)

(XXI)

or

(XXII)

Recently another member of this series has been isolated from the medicinal leaves of *Didymocarpus pedicellata* in this laboratory. It has been named pedicellic acid¹⁷ (XXIII).

14. M. Asano, Y. Kameda, T. Komai, and I. Ishino, "Igakusorun" I, 1945, p. 41.

15. A. Stoll, G. Ranz, and A. Brack, *Experientia*, 1947, 3, 111, 115.16. V. C. Barry and D. Twomay, *Proc. Roy. Irish Acad.*, 1952, 55, Sec. B, No. 1, 1.

17. K. V. Rao, T. R. Seshadri, and M. S. Sood, Paper read in the International Symposium on the Chemistry of Natural Products, Tokyo, p. 162, 1964.

and its constitution has been determined as α -methyl- α' -tridecylsuccinic acid, based on degradation and spectral studies.

SIMPLE SUCCINIC ACID DERIVATIVES

These discoveries provide occasion for a review of the chemistry of succinic acids and their derivatives occurring in Nature. Succinic acid and its alkylated derivatives are noted for the ready loss of water to form internal anhydrides. The more the hydrogen atoms of the ethylene group of succinic acid are substituted by alkyl groups, the more readily is anhydride formation. Succinic anhydrides afford with alcohols half-esters, which have been shown to have antitubercular activity, as mentioned above.

Succinic acid (XXIV) itself occurs in the fossil resin amber, in some lignites, and in animal fluids. It is formed in the oxidation of fats with nitric acid, in the fermentation of calcium malate or ammonium tartrate, and in alcoholic fermentation. It is an important laboratory reagent and is used for the separation of iron from aluminium. In conjunction with methylene blue on a charcoal surface, it forms a model oxidation-reduction system.

When condensed with glycols, it provides polymers of industrial importance. Succinic dibenzyl ester is used in medicine. Succinic anhydride is widely used as an intermediate in the dyestuff industry and in the preparation of many other organic compounds. Succinimide is another important derivative of succinic acid; it furnishes *N*-bromosuccinimide which is a specific brominating agent.

There are a number of acids which occur in nature and which can be considered to be derived from succinic acid and its derivatives and these are discussed below.

Fumaric acid (XXV) occurs in many plants, in Iceland moss, in *Fumaria officinalis*¹⁸, and in some fungi. It takes part in respiratory processes in animals. Maleic acid, the *cis*-isomer, is a relatively cheap organic intermediate obtained synthetically and is widely used in the laboratory and in the industry as a resin former. It is also used as a typical dienophile in the Diels-Alder reaction. *Ethyleneoxydicarboxylic acid* (XXVI) (epoxide of fumaric acid) is a mould metabolic product and has been isolated in the (-)-form from *Monilia formosa* and *Penicillium viniferum*¹⁹. *Dihydroxymaleic acid* (XXVII) occurs in herbs like *Glaucinum luteum*²⁰ and is a very important acid having strong reducing properties. In many respects it closely resembles ascorbic acid (vitamin C) and indeed this resemblance was used effectively in unravelling the constitution of ascorbic acid. Both exhibit the same oxidation-reduction reactions and they show the same change in the absorption spectra when they are subjected to oxidation.

18. Winckler, *Annalen*, 1833, 4, 230.

19. K. Sakaguchi, T. Inone, and S. Tada: ref. C. II (1937), 419; II (1938), 3825; I (1939), 4484; I (1940), 68.

20. H. Schmalzuss, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1923, 131, 166; 1924, 123, 156.

Malic acid (XXVIII) (monohydroxysuccinic acid) occurs in many plants and the common variety is the (-)-form. It occurs as calcium and potassium salts in tobacco leaves and rhubarb stalks. It can be obtained from the juice of many green fruits. In equilibrium with fumaric acid, it arises by the action of the enzyme succinodehydrogenase on succinic acid, in presence of a hydrogen acceptor. It is also involved in Kreb's cycle and it takes part in a dismutation with pyruvic acid to provide carbon dioxide and lactic acid. It is an important reagent in coumarin chemistry. It affords sulphosuccinates which are powerful detergents.

Tartaric acid (XXIX) (dihydroxysuccinic acid)¹⁸ occurs in four forms: the (+)-form is widely distributed in the vegetable world and occurs principally in grapes. It gets converted into other forms and finally into the (±)-form. Hydriodic acid reduces it to succinic acid. Its uses are many and range from food and confectionary industries, through pharmaceutical products, to plastics and sequestering agents.

Aspartic acid (XXX) (aminosuccinic acid) like malic acid also occurs in the (-)-form. It is found in sugarcane, sugarbeet, and in mulberry leaves. In the animal kingdom its presence is observed in blood, milk, and diseased tissues. It can be converted into succinic acid when treated with glucose under pressure, but under mild conditions it affords a brown compound with carbohydrates, believed to be the cause of darkening in fruits. It is an effective aminating agent. Its frequent occurrence with aspartase in germinating seedlings in the nodules of legumes and in the tubers of potatoes indicates its biological importance, probably in the trans-amination of α-keto-acids or in the building up of the reserve glycogens. β-Asparagine (XXXI) is a β-amide of aspartic acid and occurs naturally in the (-)-form. It is widely distributed in the plant kingdom, especially in the legumes. An aqueous solution of asparagine is converted into aspartic acid by *Bacillus pyocyaneus* and further into succinic acid.

Oxaloacetic acid (XXXII) (ketosuccinic acid) occurs in pea plants and it is considered to be an intermediate in the conversion of citric acid into malic acid. Its diethyl ester, oxaloacetic ester, has important applications in synthetic chemistry. Oxaloacetic acid has biochemical importance as a member of the tricarboxylic acid cycle, concerned in the animal body with the conversion of pyruvate and acetate, obtained in the metabolism of carbohydrates and fats to CO₂. Since it arises either by oxidative deamination or trans-deamination of aspartic acid, it is also an important intermediate in the metabolism of amino-acids. Its oxime (XXXIII) is found to occur in the nodules of leguminous plants²¹ during the fixation of nitrogen and passes over into aspartic acid.

(XXIV)

(XXV)

(XXVI)

(XXVII)

(XXVIII)

(XXIX)

21. A. I. Virtanen and T. Laine, *Nature*, 1938, 141, 748; 142, 165; *Biochem. J.*, 1939, 33, 412.

Even the tricarboxylic acids like tricarballic acid (XXXIV), aconitic acid (XXXV), citric (XXXVI), isocitric (XXXVII), and hydroxycitric (XXXVIII) acids are of interest in the study of succinic acid derivatives because these can be easily converted into succinic acid by simple reactions like re-reduction and decarboxylation. These also occur in plant sources,

The relation between citric acid and succinic acid is intimate because they are members of the fatty acid cycle and the latter arises from the former; starting from aspartate, which yields oxaloacetic acid by deamination, the cycle is briefly indicated below:

Though alkylated saturated dicarboxylic acids have only occasionally been isolated from natural sources, the corresponding unsaturated acids have been encountered more often. Thus *mesaconic acid* (XXXIX) is found in cabbage²⁹ and may be reduced to methylsuccinic acid by hydrogenation. *Itaconic acid* (XL) occurs in the juice of sugarcane and is

produced industrially by its fermentation with *Aspergillus terreus* or *A. itaconicus*²³. It has found some application for the preparation of polymeric esters with glycols. β -Ethylmalic acid (XLI) occurs in the juice of *Euphrobia highlandulosa*²⁴ and can be converted into ethylsuccinic acid by reduction. α -Methylmalic acid (XLII) has been recently isolated in the (-)-form from the skins of a special variety of apples²⁵ and has been called citramalic acid. It was obtained as the racemic synthetic compound nearly a hundred year ago. It could be considered to arise by the partial decarboxylation of citric acid.

There are only three acids occurring in nature as alkylated succinic acids. These are 2, 2-dimethylsuccinic acid (XLIII)²⁶, which appears in the urine of rats fed on a diet producing liver necrosis, roccellic acid (XLIV)²⁶, which is a lichen acid and occurs in a number of lichens, and pedicellic acid (XXIII), which has been recently isolated from the leaves of the medicinal plant *Didymocarpus pedicellata*¹⁷.

Various other acids are known to occur in nature, which can be converted into alkylated succinic acids by simple reactions. As analogue of itaconic acid, protolichesterinic acid (XLV) can be mentioned. This occurs in two forms: (+) in *Cetraria islandica* and (-) in *Cetraria crispa*²⁷. Nephromopsis acid (XLVI) is a reduced form of protolichesterinic acid and occurs in *Nephromopsis strachevi*²⁸ along with other related acids. On reduction, both the acids give rise to $\alpha\alpha'$ -disubstituted succinic acid. Lichesterinic acid (XVIII), which occurs in *Cetraria islandica*²⁹, belongs to the mesaconic acid type and has the above properties. Another member is nephrosterinic acid (XLVII) and is found in *Nephromopsis endocrocea*³⁰. It belongs to itaconic acid type and always accompanies its reduced

23. K. Kinoshita, ref. C. I. (1932), 2964; C. T. Calam, A. E. Oxford, and H. Raistrick, *Biochem. J.*, 1939, **33**, 1488.

24. N. P. Kirjalow : ref. C. II (1940), 773.

25. A. C. Hulme, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1954, **114**, 36.

26. Y. Sakurai, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1941, **61**, 108, 45.

27. W. Zopf, *Flechtenstoffe*, 1907, 15; M. Asano, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1927, **47**, 1.

28. M. Asano and C. Azumi, *Ber.*, 1935, **68**, 995.

29. Y. Asahina and M. Yasore, *Ber.*, 1932, **65**, 1175.

30. Y. Asahina et al., *Ber.* 1935, **68**, 1558; 1937, **70**, 227.

product, *nephrosteranic acid* (XLVIII)³². These acids are important because of their antibacterial activity.

(XLV) : R = C₉H₂₇.
(XLVII) : R = C₁₁H₂₃.

(XLVI) : R = C₁₃H₂₇.
(XLVIII) : R = C₁₁H₂₇.

CHEMICAL COMPONENTS OF *ROCCELLA MONTAGNEI*

Roccella montagnei is a leafy lichen found in plenty on the coastal areas of India. It is frequently eaten by cattle. More than 25 years ago, we had occasion to examine a sample growing at Waltair. Besides erythrin (XLIX), lecanoric (XX), and roccellic acids (XLIV), which have been known earlier, we isolated a new compound, which we named *montagnetol*³¹. The constitution of lecanoric acid was well known and its synthesis had earlier been achieved by Emil Fischer³². It is an important depside and has been the basis of the manufacture of litmus and certain other dyes, named archil and cudbear, commonly used in medieval times. A convenient method of its synthesis has been carried out recently³³ using dicyclohexyl carbodi-imide for the condensation of two orsellinic acid units. This avoids the laborious steps that had to be adopted earlier. Erythrin is a combination of lecanoric acid and a tetrahydric alcohol, erythritol (VII). There was some uncertainty about its constitution as to whether the alcohol group was located between the two orsellinic acid units or the compound was an ester of lecanoric acid. That the latter is the correct constitution has been shown by the unambiguous method^{34,35} of methylation, followed by hydrolysis.

Montagnetol, a related substance, was obtained both in the optically active and inactive forms. It was shown to be the erythryl ester of orsellinic acid. Though the alcohol involved is in the *meso*-form, when it is esterified with orsellinic acid, asymmetry is introduced and the compound is optically active. It racemises fairly easily and the racemic form could be obtained also from erythrin by partial hydrolysis.

The other important acid, roccellic acid, occurs commonly in many other species of *Roccella*. Nolan and co-workers³⁶ studied it in detail. It is an optically active dicarboxylic acid, having the formula C₁₇H₃₀O₄, m.p. 135°, and readily forms anhydride, anilide, and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazide. They found that it exhibited considerable similarity to the succinic acid derivatives, obtained earlier as degradation products of caproic acid and lichesterinic acid. Based on this analogy, they considered it to be α -methyl- α' -dodecyl-

31. V. S. Rao and T. R. Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, 15A, 18, 420.

32. E. Fischer and M. Fischer, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 1138.

33. S. Neelakantan, R. Padmasini, and T. R. Seshadri, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 510; *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1962, No. 7, 287.

34. Y. Sakurai, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1941, 61, 45.

35. V. S. Rao and T. R. Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, 16A, 23, 50.

36. G. Kenned, J. Breen, J. Kane, and T. J. Nolan, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1944, 64, 203.

succinic acid. They also effected an important transformation by the action of phosphorus pentabromide on roccellic acid and obtained an inactive form having m.p. 82°. They carried out the synthesis in order to prove the constitution, using as components *n*-dodecyl iodide (LI) and ester of $\alpha\text{-}\beta$ -propanetricarboxylic acid (LII). The resulting dodecyl-derivative was hydrolysed and decarboxylated to furnish a succinic acid of the desired structure. Though it did not agree with the natural acid, it had m.p. 81°, corresponding to the inactive transformation product. Nevertheless, this synthesis established the constitution of roccellic acid.

Later roccellic acid and its derivatives assumed considerable importance because of their exhibiting antibacterial activity against tuberculosis bacteria. Barry and Twomey¹⁶ studied the mixture of Na-salts of roccellic acid's half-esters (XXII) for their activity against *Myc. tuberculosis* and found them inhibiting the growth in broth for six weeks at a dilution of $2 \times 10^5 - 4 \times 10^5$. In presence of 5% human serum, however, these figures are reduced to 1×10^4 to 2×10^4 . Despite this strong serum antagonism, the mixture of half-esters have been used under the name B.53 for the cure of tuberculosis ulcer by topical application. This property of alkylated succinic acid derivatives led to continued investigation into the chemotherapy of tuberculosis. Various alkyl-substituted succinic acids were synthesised and tested to find out a potent drug. It was shown by Barry¹⁶ that compared with half-esters of alkylated succinic acids, the half-amides (LIII) and related pyrrolidine derivatives (LIV) were more effective.

[R = alkyl groups].

As mentioned earlier, *Rocella montagnei* has been occasionally used as fodder for cattle. In this connection the recent study of Krishnamurty and Subramanian³⁷ that it is rich in β -carotene may be significant because β -carotene is a well-known precursor of vitamin-A.

I wish to record my thanks to Dr. M. S. Sood for help during the lecture and in the preparation of this manuscript.